

Guide for applicants

(IMPETUS accelerator call 2023)

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Call opens: 10th January 2023, 12:00 pm (noon) CET

Call closes: 13th March 2023, 12:00 pm (noon) CET

Deadlines will be strictly adhered to. Any submission past the deadline will not be considered.

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Introduction

This guide is designed to support citizen science initiatives considering a submission to the first IMPETUS Accelerator Call (2023). **It is intended to be the main source of information for the call.** Therefore, in case of factual conflicts with other sources of information (such as the IMPETUS website), **the contents of this guide should be deemed authoritative.**

Should you have any outstanding queries regarding the application process after reading this document, please attend one of our webinars, refer to the FAQ on our website, or contact us at opencall@impetus4cs.eu or on our social media channels.

What is IMPETUS?

IMPETUS is a project funded by the European Commission to support and give recognition to citizen science in Europe.

IMPETUS' goal is to

- enable more diverse citizen science initiatives to access funding;
- bring citizen science closer to society and policy makers;
- acknowledge the role of citizen science in tackling the greatest challenges of our times; and
- enable citizen science initiatives to contribute to Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goal commitments.

IMPETUS will do this by directly **funding and supporting citizen science initiatives** selected through open calls; awarding the **European Union Prize for Citizen Science** to outstanding projects; and developing **resources that help citizen science initiatives** become more impactful and sustainable.

This open accelerator call is for **funding and support for citizen science initiatives**.

IMPETUS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme. It is delivered by [Zabala](#), [King's College London](#), [Science for Change](#), [T6 Ecosystems srl](#), [EUSEA](#), [Ars Electronica](#), and [Nesta UK](#). It started in July 2022 and will run until June 2026.

What is citizen science?

IMPETUS takes an inclusive view on citizen science. We broadly follow the [Green Paper on Citizen Science for Europe](#) from January 2014, which defines it as the public participating *“in scientific research activities, when citizens actively contribute to science either with their intellectual effort or surrounding knowledge or with their tools and resources.”*

The term covers a range of activities with different levels of participation, from data collection in projects led by trained scientists, to co-designing research questions and policy, to science literacy and public engagement. To truly be considered citizen science it is important that projects have the intention to contribute to research, to produce new research-based knowledge, and for their activities to be carried out by participating citizens. Citizen participation is inherent to citizen science projects and their goals.

Citizen science engages volunteers in a range of scientific activities. This helps educate and inform citizens in the subject matter and leads to greater public understanding of how science and scientists work. Participation in citizen science can increase trust in science and expert opinions, enhance critical thinking, and ultimately fight misinformation, disinformation and fake news. Scientists can learn from citizen science about what people genuinely care about, the impact their work has or should have in society, and become more participatory, by involving volunteers early on in co-designing the research, collecting, cleaning, and analysing the data, documenting the results, and sharing the recognition.

While inclusive, various types of relevant activities are not citizen science. For example: for us it is important that there is a scientific question and methodology, and that the activities are *carried out by* participating citizens.

Why take part?

Successful applicants will receive €20,000 (for new projects) or €10,000 (for ongoing projects) to help deliver a six-month citizen science project with the help of the IMPETUS team. All teams will have access to a set of services, tailored to their individual needs, including:

- Intensive training at the start of the accelerator on: project design, citizen engagement, data management and preservation, impact assessment and sustainability;
- Online mentoring during the pilot and beyond; on a diverse set of citizen science challenges, including data quality, data preservation, GDPR, research ethics, motivating participation, citizen empowerment, EDI (equality, diversity, inclusion), public engagement, targeted science communication, data journalism, and impact;
- Promotion via news on the IMPETUS website and on social media, as well as presentation opportunities at the IMPETUS conference and other related events;
- Peer learning and networking, facilitated through workshops and online tools.
- Peer-learning and networking, within and between pilot cohorts, through the IMPETUS Aperitives, creating bridges with external communities of interest.

IMPETUS will work with initiatives to understand their situation and challenges and support them in addressing them. Successful applicants may also feature as case studies in IMPETUS research.

Who is eligible?

Individuals, legal entities and consortia established in a country or territory in the European Research Area. This includes the European Union, all overseas countries and territories linked to EU member states (Aruba, Bonaire, Curaçao, French Polynesia, French Southern and Antarctic Territories, Greenland, New Caledonia, Saba, Saint Barthélemy, Sint Eustatius, Sint Maarten, St Pierre and Miquelon), and all third countries associated to or currently negotiating an association agreement with Horizon Europe (for the 2023 iteration of the Call: Albania, Armenia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Georgia, Iceland, Israel, Kosovo, Moldova, Montenegro, Morocco, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, United Kingdom).

For consortia, all applicants must be eligible. They must choose a lead who will submit the application and engage with IMPETUS on their behalf. Every entity is allowed to participate in one application, either on its own or as part of a consortium.

Two types of grants are available:

- Projects that are no more than six months into their citizen science journey and are yet to establish a community and/or data collection and processing procedures, can apply for a **Kickstarting grant**, worth 20,000 €. We aim to award 30 kickstarting grants in this first call.
- Projects that are more advanced, with established processes, an engaged community, and initial evidence of impact, can apply for a **Sustaining grant**, worth 10,000 €. We expect these grants to be awarded for the continuation, enhancing of impact, and/or further establishment of existing projects. We aim to award 5 sustaining grants in this first call.

IMPETUS has the following conflict of interest policy: **Immediate family, domestic and non-domestic partners and those with financial ties to members of the IMPETUS team are prohibited to apply.** If you have a prior relationship with anyone contributing to IMPETUS that you feel may constitute a conflict of interest, please email opencall@impetus4cs.eu for clarification.

What is supported?

IMPETUS will provide funding for a six-month project, which must be implemented during the IMPETUS acceleration program, scheduled to take place between June and December 2023.

All applications for either grant have to be clearly related to one of our challenges. Projects in which citizens will produce data to help with scientific inquiries needs to include in their application how data will be managed during and after the project, **including, if relevant, any GDPR and ethical concerns.**

The funding can be spent on salaries, equipment, consumables, travel, subcontracting to other entities, and indirect expenditure (calculated as 25% of the total direct costs), in accordance with Horizon Europe guidelines. ([See here for an accessible overview.](#))

In your application, you will be asked to describe your staff and resources you plan to mobilise for this amount. You may propose any cost items deemed eligible and relevant for the delivery of your project. See Annex 1 of this document for further explanation.

The activities you plan to carry out with IMPETUS cannot receive double funding. Synergies with other sources of funding, including other Horizon Europe projects, are encouraged as long as the grants are used for complementary, not overlapping purposes.

What happens with your results?

All results and outcomes of your project will remain your property, including associated objects and IP.

We expect all participants to follow an open science / source approach, sharing results and experiences widely with the community. Applicants will have to be clear in their applications about the data that will be collected or generated through the project. We will give priority to those applications that have a well-articulated plan, as well as proposals that are committed to making their data available for reuse, following an open science approach. IMPETUS will provide technical, legal and operational support to successful applicants to do so.

In addition, IMPETUS requires projects funded through the programme to collect, manage and share data with and for the IMPETUS team. This may include the contributions of the citizens, as well as anonymised and/or aggregated data on citizen participation. Both are needed for the IMPETUS team to tailor their support and resources and maximise the positive impacts of the project.

In addition, IMPETUS or the European Commission may ask you to present your work as part of our public relations and networking events, in order to showcase the benefits of the programme.

How is the IMPETUS Accelerator Call organised?

Three calls

IMPETUS will implement three open accelerator calls, one per year, starting in 2023. **This document refers to the first accelerator call only.**

Topics

IMPETUS supports citizen science initiatives addressing two challenges per call. For this first open call, these topics are *Healthy Planet* and *Cities for Life*.

As noted earlier, our understanding of citizen science is inclusive. We are seeking to fund projects that can make a difference, at local, national or international scale. We are particularly interested in applications that propose novel, less explored participatory roles for citizens and other key stakeholders, and that engage with marginalised, underrepresented or disadvantaged groups.

In our short proposal form (see Annex 2: Application form) you will be asked to clearly articulate the aim and scope of your citizen science initiative, including the overall idea, implementation, team, and expected impact.

Application process

Please note that IMPETUS has parallel open calls for the IMPETUS Accelerator, and the European Union Prize for Citizen Science. While you may be eligible to apply for both of them, the applications are independent, and you will need to apply for either on a different platform. Please also use the guidance provided on the website www.impetus4cs.eu/opencall to identify which call you are eligible for.

Submission for the IMPETUS Accelerator will be [online via the EasyChair platform](#). On this platform, applicants will be asked questions to determine their eligibility to apply for funding, as well as

their ability to conduct the pilot. All information provided must be in English. Only complete applications submitted before the deadline will be considered for review.

All applications will be reviewed by a panel of experts selected by the IMPETUS team. The reviewers will shortlist applications for a remote interview. We anticipate interviews to be held between 10th and 14th April 2023. Successful candidates will be invited to join the IMPETUS accelerator for six months, following a short negotiation. As part of the negotiation phase, candidates will join the IMPETUS Bootcamp, a week-long online workshop that will enable them to revise their project plans and timeline, milestones and deliverables, based on best practice in citizen science.

How to apply

1. The starting point for your application is the IMPETUS website. Go to www.impetus4cs.eu/opencall
2. Read this guide, as well as the FAQ and related tutorials available on that page.
3. Use the eligibility assessment tool on the website to identify which call you can apply for.
4. Create an account on the EasyChair platform and start your application.
5. Make sure to answer all questions and upload all relevant documents. These documents are:
 - a. A short proposal. A copy is available in [Annex 2: Application form](#) or at <https://impetus4cs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Application-form-2023.docx>
 - b. A dated and signed declaration of honour. A copy is available in [Annex 2](#) or at <https://impetus4cs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Declaration-of-honour-2023.docx>
6. Submit before the deadline, at noon (CET) on the 13th March 2023.

The comments in the proposal form template will help you cover all aspects we will consider when reviewing your application. **It is very important that you do not change the template in any way** - any attempt to do so, no matter how minor, may result in your application being discarded without a review. This includes changes to the font size. The maximum length for applications is four (4) pages.

You can upload multiple versions of the documents and make multiple submissions. We will consider only the last version received before the deadline.

How we select proposals

Step 1 – Eligibility checks

IMPETUS checks if eligibility criteria are met. Proposals considered not eligible will not proceed to Step 2. The criteria are listed under [Who is](#).

Step 2 – Reviews and shortlist

Eligible proposals will be evaluated by at least two reviewers against the following criteria:

1. Idea
2. Implementation
3. Team and Community
4. Impact

Reviewers will be asked to provide a score on a five-point scale for each criterion. Applications that reach at least 12 points overall, and no less than three points in each area, will be invited for interview. A detailed list of criteria is available in [Annex 5: Review criteria](#). Consider them when filling in the proposal template.

Step 3 – Interview

Shortlisted applicants will be invited to a remote interview with an expert panel. The interview will consist of a short pitch of the application, followed by questions. The interviews will be scheduled between 11th and 18th April 2023. To grant call winners access to funding quickly, we operate on a very tight schedule - we plan to send out invitations to interviews by 6th April 2023, including a time slot for the interview. **We will not be able to negotiate interview dates** and related conditions with the applicants and may not answer any queries on the subject. If an applicant is not able to attend the interview, we will have to reject that application.

Applicants who were not shortlisted will also be informed at this stage.

Step 4 – Decisions

After the interview, the panel will decide whether to accept the applicant into the programme. We will provide feedback to applicants to improve their pilot. We will not be able to reply to any queries on unsuccessful applications. Decisions will be final and cannot be contested. We plan to inform applicants about the outcome by 19th April 2023.

What happens when you are selected

Negotiation

If your application is successful, you will be invited to enter negotiations with IMPETUS. This is a busy two-month period, which will hopefully end with a signed contract between you and IMPETUS. For this to happen, we will have to complete the following steps:

- **Due diligence checks:** these checks are performed to understand the status of the applicant. We will check your legal entity information, ethics requirements, financial information and any other checks as requested by the European Commission before commencing the project. Should you fail the due diligence checks, IMPETUS reserves the right to reject the application.
- **Matchmaking event:** This allows the selected pilots to meet with mentors who will accompany them during the accelerator, and is an online meeting, including a 3-minute pitch where pilots explain their project and the potential need for mentoring, and time for pilots and mentors to determine their mutual suitability.
- **Workplan and budget agreement:** before starting the project, the applicant and IMPETUS agree on milestones and success criteria. We will also assess the costs associated with your project to ensure they are eligible. You will be assigned a mentor who will go through this process with you and answer any questions.
- **Bootcamp:** As part of the negotiations, once you have prepared your preliminary work plan, we will host an online workshop that you will need to attend. This workshop will help you to flesh out the details of your work plan and budget; contracts will be signed after this is complete.

Negotiations will start mid-April 2023 and must finish (with a signed contract, see [Annex 6: Negotiation documents](#)) by the mid-June 2023. A detailed schedule will be sent out in due time.

The IMPETUS accelerator

Applicants who reach this stage of the process are formally accepted into the six-month accelerator between 15th June and 15th December 2023.

The IMPETUS accelerator will provide selected pilots with resources and training, tailored to the needs of each citizen science project, as outlined in the [Why take part](#) section.

Funds will be transferred in two stages – 50% at the beginning of the project, and the remaining 50% at the end. To qualify for the funding in totality, participants must complete all of the activities outlined below:

- Implement a six-month project as agreed during the negotiation phase and specified in the contract;
- Attend training, webinars, and co-design workshops;
- Attend monthly update calls with mentor and / or other pilots;
- Attend the IMPETUS Aperitive meetings every other month;
- Provide a formal report outlining your activities at the mid-term point and end of the pilot;
- Provide a pictures, text, and a short video about your work to be shared on the IMPETUS website and social media channels;
- Present your project at events as and when possible – all projects should allocate a portion of their budget to outreach activities;
- Acknowledge IMPETUS funding, and conduct outreach activities about IMPETUS to your network;

- Participate in IMPETUS impact assessment activities, such as:
 - Complete an impact assessment canvas
 - Send at least one survey to your citizen scientists (or organize another process for data gathering from them)
 - Compile a quali-quantitative impact assessment report following the methodology described in the IMPETUS training
 - Answer a dedicated questionnaire and/or provide needed data about achieved impacts
- Attend an interview with and provide feedback to the IMPETUS team.

Annex 1: Eligible costs

Overview

IMPETUS' citizen science fund is provided by Horizon Europe, a large research and innovation programmes funded by taxpayers. Accelerated projects are responsible to ensure the funds are spent in accordance to Horizon Europe guidelines. IMPETUS will provide training and guidance to all funded pilots on financial matters. The following provides a summary of these guidelines.

The grants may be spent only on eligible costs. These are costs that meet the following criteria:

- Incurred by the applicant in connection with or during the project;
- Identifiable and verifiable in the applicant's accounts;
- Compliant with national law;
- Reasonable, justified, in accordance with sound financial management (economy and efficiency);
- Indicated in the budget you submitted with the short proposal.

Cost categories and reimbursement guidelines

The budget you submit will have to include different cost categories, which are explained below. There is a general distinction between **direct costs**, **subcontracting**, and **indirect costs** (also known as overheads). Indirect costs are calculated at 25% of the direct costs; no indirect costs can be charged on subcontracting.

All costs, except for purchased equipment (see below), are recovered 100%, and need to include the indirect costs, charged on top of the total direct costs. All costs should be stated inclusive of any irrecoverable VAT.

Direct costs: Personnel (100% reimbursed + indirect costs)

Applicants can spend IMPETUS funds on staff who are directly involved in the execution of the project.

Direct costs: Equipment (12.5% reimbursed + indirect costs)

Equipment with a useful life in excess of the project duration can only be reimbursed to the extent the asset would be depreciated for the six-month project period. Therefore, the standard rate allowed under the contracted project will be 12.5% of the total costs of the asset for a six-month period. Indirect costs can be applied to the 12.5% of costs charged to the project.

The costs of equipment rental for the project period can be charged at full cost, as long as the rental cost is not greater than the depreciation cost, had the equipment been purchased.

Direct costs: Consumables, other goods and services (100% reimbursed + indirect costs)

Applicants can spend funds on consumables and other goods and services (including travel), if they are directly relevant for the completion of the project.

There is no hard-and-fast rule about the distinction between equipment and other costs; small items such as sensors may be budgeted as 'other goods and services'.

Subcontracting (100% reimbursed, no indirect costs)

Applicants may subcontract some of their activities to other parties as long as they are also from an eligible country (see [Who is](#)). No indirect costs can be charged on subcontracting costs. Note that we expect the applicant to carry out most of the tasks of the project – subcontracting cannot be used to carry out key tasks in the project.

Indirect costs

Indirect costs are within the €20,000 limit for kickstarting projects and €10,000 limit for sustaining projects, and cover items such as rent, administration, printing, photocopying, amenities etc. These costs are eligible if they are declared on the basis of the flat rate of 25% of the eligible costs, excluding costs of subcontracting.

Annex 2: Application form

Proposal Title

Summary

<i>Provide a brief overview of your proposed project</i>

1. Idea

<i>Describe the core idea of your application in <u>one</u> sentence.</i>
<i>How will your project contribute to current societal challenges? How does it relate to the IMPETUS challenge?</i>
<i>How is your project different from others? What is new or different about it?</i>
<i>Which territories will your project cover? Be specific: note countries, regions, cities etc. as relevant</i>
<i>Who are the key stakeholders? Who will be (positively or negatively) impacted by the project and how?</i>

2. Implementation

How will you engage your existing and/or new citizen scientists? What will they be asked to do, what data will they collect or produce? How many citizen scientists do you (plan to) engage?

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***Beyond the activities described above, what activities will your team participate in?
E.g. public dissemination, research publications, meetings with stakeholders, etc.***

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How do you intend to attract and maintain engagement from citizen scientists and other stakeholders? Why will people want to contribute?

--

Which data or other outputs do you intend to gather or produce? How much of this will be openly available? Have you already published anything? Where?

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Do you rely on personal data? If so, how will you store it? What (if any) other ethical challenges does your project pose?

--

How will you use the budget?			
Budget category	Cost over 6 months	Overheads (25%)	Total in Euro
Personnel			
Travel			
Equipment			
Other goods and services			
Subcontracting		n/a	
Grand total in Euro			
Briefly explain the main cost items.			

3. Team & Community

<i>Which activities in your proposed project will involve citizen scientists and/or the public?</i>
<i>Who are the core members of your team? What are their relevant skills and experience?</i>
<i>What expertise are you missing? How could IMPETUS help?</i>

How is or will your project team (including citizen scientists) be inclusive and diverse? How will it benefit underrepresented groups in Europe?

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4. Impact

What are the end-benefits of your project? What do you want to achieve? How will things be different at the end of the six months? How about in a year, or five, or a decade?

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What positive changes do you expect for your stakeholders by the end of the project? Please mention specific stakeholder groups (such as researchers, citizens, decision-makers, etc.).

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Why is participating in IMPETUS important to you? What problem will it allow you to address that you could not otherwise achieve?

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How will you ensure the sustainability of the work beyond the end of the funding? Indicate any additional sources of funding/support you may need and how you plan to secure it.

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How will your participation in IMPETUS make your project more sustainable?

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Annex 3: Declaration of honour

Declaration of honour

1. I declare:
 - a. the organisation that I represent is not bankrupt or being wound up, is not having its affairs administered by the courts, has not entered into an arrangement with creditors, has not suspended business activities, is not the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, nor is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations;
 - b. neither the organisation that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgment which has the force of res judicata;
 - c. neither the organisation that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organisations;
 - d. the organisation that I represent is in compliance with its obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed;
 - e. neither the organisation that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been the subject of a judgment which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organisation or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests;
 - f. the organisation that I represent is not subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information, or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget.
 - g. the proposed project does not receive funding for the same activities from other sources.
2. I declare that I:
 - a. am not subject to a conflict of interest;
 - b. have not made false declarations in supplying the information required as a condition of participation in the IMPETUS call or did not fail to supply this information;
 - c. am not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the above-mentioned points 1a) to 1f).
3. I certify that I:
 - a. am committed to participate in the project;
 - b. have stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain activity throughout participation in the project and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;
 - c. have or will have the necessary resources as and when needed to carry out involvement in the project.
4. I declare that I and other representatives of my organisation will:
 - a. ensure the quality, integrity and accuracy of research activities and outputs within the scope of the project;

- b. ensure informed consent of any and all volunteers taking part in the project, both data subjects (such as in the case of surveys) and project participants (such as citizen scientists);
- c. take all steps to protect and ensure the confidentiality of all project participants;
- d. take all necessary steps to protect vulnerable groups who may participate within the project (particularly minors and those with a reduced capacity for consent);
- e. actively seek to encourage participation from underrepresented groups;
- f. comply with any and all legal requirements, both within the country or countries in which the project shall operate and at the European level, in particular the European Union General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679;
- g. take all reasonable steps to ensure project outputs are made openly available and accessible to the widest possible audience, where this does not infringe upon the rights and expectations of project participants, or contravene the legal requirements of the territories in which the project shall operate.

I declare that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, I am eligible to apply for the IMPETUS accelerator call and all the information I provided in the form is true.

Name	
Signature	
Date	

Annex 5: Review criteria

All four areas will be weighted equally by reviewers on a scale of 1-5.

Please consider that expectations differ slightly between kickstarting and sustaining project applications.

		Kickstarting projects	Sustaining projects
Idea	Relevance to the topic	Is the project in scope of IMPETUS' definition of citizen science? Does the project focus on the <i>Healthy Planet</i> theme and one of the subtopics (Water, Land, Biodiversity), or <i>Cities for Life</i> .	
	Aims of the project	Does the project have clearly defined, ambitious and achievable goals? Will the project contribute to current societal challenges? Is there a clear research question?	Does the project have clearly defined sustainability goals? Does the project contribute to current societal challenges?
	Complementarity to IMPETUS goals	Does the project pursue a new, innovative idea? Does it use new techniques, activities and technologies, or focus on a new problem or area of application?	Does the project plan to become more sustainable? Are the project goals aligned with IMPETUS' goals for sustainability, engagement, and inclusion?
Implementation	Planned activities	Can the project goals be achieved on the scale proposed, with the resources and team proposed? Does the project consider ethical implications of its work?	
	Commitment to open science	Does the project follow open science principles? Will project data and outputs be openly accessible? Does the approach account for data protection and any personal or sensitive data?	Does the project follow open science principles? Does the project publish its results and insights, or does it plan to? Does the approach account for data protection and any personal or sensitive data?
	Use of resources	Are the requested resources relevant and suitable for the proposal? Can the project feasibly be carried out using the funding and resources requested? Are there any important activities or requirements (such as dissemination) that are not accounted for within the budget?	
Team and community	Citizen engagement	Are the planned activities achievable and accessible to citizen scientists? Do they have sufficient capacity to conduct engagement at the proposed scale? Is there an effective strategy to engage existing or new citizen scientists in the project activities? Are citizens engaged in activities other than data gathering?	Does the project have an active citizen scientist community engaged in different activities? Is there an effective strategy for continuous engagement? Are the planned activities achievable and accessible to citizen scientists?
	Interdisciplinarity	Does the team have experience of research activities, managing communities, citizen science etc.? Have they identified relevant expertise gaps and ways to fill those gaps? Does the team involve experts from different disciplines?	

	Inclusion & Diversity	Does the project actively engage underrepresented groups (LGBTQ+, low-income country, ethnic minority, refugee, disabled), or will these groups clearly benefit from the project? Is the project non-male led?	
Impact	Anticipated impact	Will the project benefit the citizen scientists taking part, or the community in which it will take place? Will the project have significant impact in the realms of environment, science, society, economy, or democracy?	Does the project benefit its existing citizen science community? Will the project significantly increase or sustain existing impact in the realms of environment, science, society, economy, or democracy?
	Additionality of IMPETUS funding	Will the project benefit from IMPETUS funding? Will the project benefit from the IMPETUS accelerator? Will there be significant additional value through participation in IMPETUS?	
	Sustainability	Is there a sustainability concept? Are the project and outputs maintainable beyond the life of the project? Are new sources of funding available or likely to become available? Will participation in IMPETUS improve the longevity of the project?	Is there a sustainability concept? Are past project results maintained, and will they remain so? Are new sources of funding available or likely to become available; are they necessary? Will participation in IMPETUS improve the longevity of the project?

Annex 6: Negotiation documents

If you have passed the interview stage, you will be asked to submit a series of documents, as explained in this section.

1. Administrative documentation

For legal entities: We will ask you to demonstrate the legal existence of your organisation.

Legal existence: Company Register, Official Journal and so forth, showing the name of the organization, the legal address and registration number and, if applicable, a copy of a document proving VAT registration (in case the VAT number does not show on the registration extract or its equivalent).

In a consortium of several organisations, we will be carrying out this step for each organisation.

In case of natural persons (individuals), that do not participate as a legal entity:

- A copy of the ID-card or passport of participant(s) in the project team will be required.
- A proof for every participant in the project that (s)he is legally established and working in an eligible country

2. Project plan

During negotiations, the IMPETUS team will work with you to finalise a project plan for the accelerator. Receiving any amount of funding from IMPETUS requires you to **set and achieve** a set of milestones and/or KPIs. During this time, we will also provide more details on the workshops and other events you will need to attend.

The project plan will include a budget. IMPETUS may request adjustments the budget outlined by the applicant in the original submission based on feedback received during the interview. The project plan will be finalised after the IMPETUS bootcamp.

3. Contract

Once a project plan has been agreed, you will be asked to sign a contract to formally join the IMPETUS accelerator. A preliminary template of the contract will be made available in due time. The terms of the contract are the same for every pilot accepted into the accelerator and cannot be negotiated.

The contract must be signed by the legal representative of your project / organisation.

When pilots are delivered by a consortium the contract will be signed by the leading organisation.

When pilots are delivered by a group of individuals, the contract will be signed by the pilot coordinator.

4. Bank account information

If negotiations are successful, IMPETUS will require bank account information of where to transfer the funding. Applicants will be asked to fill out this [bank information template](#) that will be provided as an Annex of the contract. For consortia of organizations, payments will be made to the leading entity only. For groups of individuals, payments will be made to the coordinator of the project.

In the case of organizations, the bank information document will have to be signed (and, if applicable, stamped) by the legal representative of the organisation. Use CAPITAL LETTERS and LATIN CHARACTERS when completing the form.

The form will also need to be signed by your bank to validate the information you have provided. Alternatively, you can provide a recent bank statement which confirms the details you have included in the form.

Please note that bank account information forms will not be accepted until they are signed by the organisation representative and approved by your bank (or bank statement provided).

5. Other documents

IMPETUS reserves the right to solicit any other document that allows us to assess the capacity and capability of the applicants to deliver the pilot.